

Simplified Model for Partially-Composite Precast Concrete Insulated Wall Panels Subjected to Lateral Loading

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ABSTRACT

A simplified model to predict the partially composite response of precast concrete insulated wall panels to lateral loading is proposed. A conventional insulated wall panel design consists of two concrete wythes which sandwich a foam insulation layer. Shear ties are used to connect the two concrete wythes through the insulation layer – these ties can be designed to resist flexural demands via composite, partially composite or non-composite action of the section. Numerous types and configurations of shear ties (many of them proprietary) are available with a large range of constitutive properties, and thus the response of a wall panel can vary based on the type of tie used in its construction. Standard design practices do not consider the constitutive properties of the tie, compatibility of the wythes, or locations of the ties within the panel. A simplified model is proposed which incorporates the relative shear tie deformation as well as the tie's constitutive properties. The approach superimposes the sum of the force couple developed in each shear tie and the capacity of each concrete wythe via an iterative process by which the strength, deformation and level of composite action is calculated at each load increment. This model provides an accurate estimate of the load-deformation responses of these panels when subjected to lateral loads (perpendicular to the panel). The method is used to illustrate the sensitivity of flexural response in a precast insulated wall panel to tie properties and placement. The proposed model is demonstrated to be an effective tool for efficient flexural performance-based design and selective detailing of precast concrete insulated wall panels.

Keywords: Insulated wall panel, Partially-composite behavior, Precast concrete, Shear tie

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25 1. INTRODUCTION

26 Energy efficiency in buildings has become a major concern due to the threat of climate
27 change and the increasing cost of utilities. Collins [1] demonstrated that energy saving benefits
28 could be achieved by using a composite cladding system comprised of two concrete wythes
29 (interior and exterior) with insulating foam sandwiched between them. The insulated wall panel
30 concept further developed with research on the effect of insulation properties on the flexural
31 stiffness of panels by Pfiefer and Hanson [2]. With the recent emphasis on sustainable
32 construction, researchers and developers have refined the design of insulated panels to increase
33 thermal resistance without compromising the structural integrity of the wall panel [3]. Shear ties
34 are used to connect the two concrete wythes through the insulation layer – these ties can be
35 designed to resist flexural demands via composite, partially composite, or non-composite action
36 of the section. Thermally resistive shear ties comprised of carbon fiber-reinforced polymers
37 (CFRP) or glass fiber-reinforced polymers (GFRP) have been shown to provide the flexural
38 resistance required to resist the relevant design loads [4,5]. Though the thermal resistance of these
39 panels is of great importance, it is also necessary to understand the structural behavior and failure
40 limit states of these structures.

41 Accurate methods for calculating the composite response of insulated panels under service
42 and ultimate loading are necessary for proper design of the panel system. Multiple approaches to
43 assess the response of composite structures have been developed for a variety of structural
44 applications. Research on composite action has been conducted on steel-concrete composite beams
45 [6,7], concrete-timber structures [8–12], wood-based sandwich panels [13], and insulated concrete
46 panels [14,15]. Most of these approaches assume linear elastic behavior in the structural
47 components (including the shear ties) and do not account for a gap between interior surfaces of the

48 structural materials where shear transfer occurs. Shear transfer relies on a combination of friction
49 between the insulation and concrete layers with the combined shear loading mechanism in the ties.
50 Although experimental research has shown that a partial degree of composite action can be
51 achieved through friction between the layers [16], the ties are needed to ensure shear capacity
52 under service and ultimate loading. The gap created by the presence of the insulation layer between
53 the wythes results in the development of shear, flexure and potentially axial force in the ties as the
54 panel undergoes flexural deformation due to lateral loading (perpendicular to the panel's exterior
55 surface). The moment developed in the ties results from a force couple created when opposing
56 shear forces, separated by an eccentricity, are transferred to both concrete wythes at the locations
57 of tie embedment. Traditional approaches are not easily extended to capture the localized flexural
58 behavior of the ties.

59 Recently, approaches have been developed specifically for insulated wall panel systems.
60 Benayoune et al. [17] showed that the ultimate strength and degree of composite action of a precast
61 wall system is highly dependent upon the stiffness of the shear tie. Salmon and Einea [14]
62 developed a method that, although effective for calculating thermal bowing deflections, is not
63 applicable for determination of flexural strength. Bai et al. [18] developed a discrete model
64 incorporating shear deformations and independent flexural behaviors of concrete wythes to create
65 models of symmetric partially composite concrete sandwich panels. The model was limited to
66 small elastic deformations and does not consider variation in deformation behavior of discretely
67 placed tie types and their corresponding failure modes. Hodicky et al. [19] performed experimental
68 testing on insulated concrete sandwich panels to examine the effect of varying geometric and
69 material properties of different FRP ties on shear flow strength. By manipulating the spacing of
70 distributed shear ties and thus the interaction surface area between the concrete and insulation, a

71 change in the overall magnitude of shear stresses between the concrete wythes was observed. Chen
72 et al. [20] conducted bending tests on eight large scale concrete sandwich panels and accounted
73 for a variation in the distribution of FRP shear ties. The results showed that different types of shear
74 ties produce varying levels of composite action, further motivating the need to include the
75 properties and spatial distribution of ties into analysis methods of sandwich panels. Tomlinson and
76 Fam [21] developed an approach to model the flexural response of partially-composite insulated
77 wall panels with varying arrangements of shear ties and wall panel geometries. This methodology
78 consists of an iterative approach that assumes a linear slip profile and integrates strain
79 discontinuities caused by the ties to obtain an updated slip profile, however, shear tie constitutive
80 properties are restricted to the elastic range. This may be suitable for elastic-brittle materials;
81 however, ductile materials, which include metals and numerous plastics will realistically yield due
82 to inter-wythe shear forces at large panel deformations.

83 This paper proposes a simplified model to assess the performance of both prestressed and
84 non-prestressed concrete insulated non-loadbearing panels under out-of-plane loading. As stated
85 in the title, the elements examined in this manuscript are insulated wall panels intended for use as
86 part of the building envelope. Use of these panels for use as roof or slab elements was not
87 considered in this paper. There are some cases such as refrigeration buildings that could also utilize
88 the design concept for the roof diaphragm, however the main application is for wall panels. These
89 elements are designed to resist of out-of-plane forces such as those generated from wind loads or
90 pressure demands from blast events.

91 As an alternative to the aforementioned methods by others, the proposed model provides a
92 simplified method for calculating panel performance from service loads through ultimate strength
93 for a wide range of cross-section geometries and shear tie configurations. The intended application

94 of the model is for use as a design and analysis tool and facilitates ease of implementation by the
95 user without the prerequisite of commercial finite element software. It allows the user to easily
96 input all relevant geometric and material parameters and determine the behavior of the panels
97 without the need for building complicated finite element models. The proposed model incorporates
98 the elastic and inelastic constitutive properties of the wythe-to-wythe shear ties, thus capturing the
99 effect of tie ductility on the overall panel. Proper use of the model enables a simplified yet effective
100 way to design and selectively detail tie arrangements for a desired level of performance and/or an
101 intended failure mode or limit state in response to lateral loads. The proposed model is particularly
102 applicable for the design of precast insulated wall panels to resist impulsive lateral loads such as
103 blast and impact.

104 **2. BACKGROUND**

105 Insulated precast concrete wall panels consist of a layer of foam insulation sandwiched
106 between two layers, or wythes, of concrete. The insulating layer allows the panel to provide high
107 thermal resistance without sacrificing the advantages offered by precast concrete construction,
108 including design aesthetics, economic fabrication with higher quality control, or rapid erection.
109 Shear ties which connect the two wythes through the insulation layer are commonly used to resist
110 the shear and tension forces generated during fabrication, shipping, erection, and service life. The
111 combinations of shear and tension on the ties vary over the loading history of the panel. In most
112 cases compression between the wythes is assumed to be transmitted through the insulation.

113 While a physical connection between the concrete wythes is necessary to create composite
114 action, this connection can allow heat to transfer directly between the wythes due to "thermal
115 bridging," thereby decreasing the thermal efficiency of the panel [22]. However, the effects of
116 thermal bridging can be diminished or effectively eliminated by utilizing shear ties made with

117 material having low thermal conductivity with small cross-sectional area. Numerous shear tie
118 systems (many of them proprietary) are currently available and offer varying levels of strength,
119 stiffness, thermal resistance and cost. Shear ties may be placed at discrete locations or distributed
120 along the length of the panel. They can be used to allow the interior and exterior wythe to work in
121 tandem to resist external lateral loads, thereby inducing flexural response in the panel. For
122 insulated panels constructed with shear ties, the flexural behavior can be classified as non-
123 composite, composite or partially composite. These scenarios are examined for a typical section
124 and span as illustrated in Figure 1A.

125 Composite behavior is defined in this paper as the flexural resistance achieved by assuming
126 a linear strain profile over the panel section (see Figure 1B), similar to that in a solid concrete
127 cross-section. Non-composite behavior exists when the interior and exterior wythes act in flexure
128 independently to resist applied loads, and the flexural contribution of the insulation layer is
129 assumed to be negligible. This is equivalent to the flexural response of two stacked slabs with a
130 frictionless interface between them. Due to compatibility, the stacked slabs must have the same
131 curvature, rotation and flexural displacement along the length. This results in measurable relative
132 slip between the two wythes (Figure 1C). Between these two extrema is the case of partially
133 composite behavior, which is characterized by a level of shear force transfer between the interior
134 and exterior wythes through the connection between them (Figure 1D). These connectors allow
135 relative slip between the panels (though less than that of non-composite panels) as a function of
136 their shear resistance. The degree of composite action dictates the moment-curvature resistance of
137 the section and hence the load-deflection behavior of the panel (Figure 1E). As the degree of shear
138 transfer increases, the response will trend toward that of a composite section – conversely,
139 decreasing levels of shear transfer will trend toward the non-composite response.

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Figure 1 - Flexural behavior of insulated concrete wall panels

142 **3. COMPUTATIONAL MODELING OF PANEL RESPONSE EXTREMA**

143 Before discussing the development and performance of the proposed approach, the authors
 144 will first illustrate the underlying mechanics of precast insulated wall panels constructed with shear
 145 ties via a computational modeling approach, implemented using OpenSees [23]. An illustration of
 146 the OpenSees model is shown in Figure 2 where C , L , and P represent the shear tie spacing, span
 147 length, and panel fabrication length, respectively. Since the model was developed in 2D, multiple
 148 rows of shear ties at the same location along the panel length are lumped together. Concrete wythes
 149 are modeled as *Displacement-Based Beam-Column Elements* [23] with ten discretized fiber cross-
 150 sections (integration points) every 30.5 cm (12 in.) along their length. Shear ties are represented
 151 with *Two Node Link Elements* [23] (Figure 2c) and assembled together to form the wall system
 152 (see Figure 2b). The flexural resistance of the insulation layer is not physically represented in this

153 model but is instead incorporated into the resistance of the discrete tie as noted in Naito et al. [24].
154 Concrete in the wythe beam-columns is modeled using a uniaxial material with non-linear
155 compression behavior and linear tension softening (material type *Concrete02* [23]). Linear
156 concrete tension softening is used to facilitate convergence when the beam-column element
157 experienced cracking. Reinforcing steel is modeled with idealized uniaxial *ElasticMultiLinear*
158 *Material* [23] stress-strain behavior.

159 The link elements consist of orthogonal springs in the direction parallel to its local principal
160 axis (*S1*) to support compression as well as transverse (*S2*) to implement the shear force-
161 deformation relationship of the ties (Figure 2d). The axial resistance of the discrete ties (*S1*) is
162 modeled using an *Elastic Uniaxial Material* [23] with constitutive properties based upon the
163 compressive stiffness of the insulation. Through experimental testing of extruded polystyrene
164 (XPS) foam, a compressive stiffness value of 0.244 kN/cm per cm² of link element tributary area
165 was deemed sufficient for use in the model. The shear-deformation behavior of the ties in the *S2*
166 springs is modelled using an *ElasticMultiLinear Material* [23] as illustrated in Figure 2d where
167 V_m and V_u represent the tie force at peak response and ultimate (i.e., fracture), respectively. D_y ,
168 D_m and D_u denote the tie deformations at the onset and end of the peak force plateau and at
169 ultimate response, respectively. This material model can be constructed using data from
170 experimental testing or tie manufacturer specifications. Link elements were discretely placed at
171 the location of every shear tie along the length of the panel and connected the corresponding nodes
172 of the two wythes with full translational and rotational connectivity. Additional link elements with
173 zero resistance in *S2* were used at intermediate nodal locations along the length of the wythe beam-
174 columns where no ties were present, as well as at the ends of the panel, to maintain overall stability
175 of the slender wythes. The analysis is conducted using a hybrid incrementation scheme,

176 incorporating both displacement and force-controlled methods. Force-controlled incrementation is
 177 used until the peak panel response is reached (i.e., tangent slope of the panel resistance function
 178 reaches zero) and the remainder of the analysis is run displacement-controlled. This hybrid
 179 approach is used to improve efficiency of the model while ensuring that all regions of panel
 180 response are properly captured.

181 a) Loaded Panel
 182 b) Numerical model
 183 c) Model details
 184 d) Shear element properties
 Figure 2 - Schematic of model built using computational methods

183 Using this computational component-based model, the effect of shear tie stiffness on the
 184 degree of composite action of a panel can be illustrated. As the stiffness of the ties approaches
 185 zero, the response of the panel approaches the non-composite response. On the contrary, when the
 186 tie stiffness approaches infinity, the response approaches composite behavior. An illustration of
 187 this concept is shown in Figure 3 where the non-composite and composite responses of a given
 188 panel are used as lower and upper bounds of strength (vice-versa for end slip), respectively. The

189 prototype wall panel considered for this study is a uniformly loaded simply-supported panel with
190 overall length and span length equal to 3.66 m (12 ft.) and 3.05 m (10 ft.), respectively;
191 symmetrical wythe cross section dimensions of 81.3 cm (32 in.) wide and 7.62 cm (3 in.) and thick;
192 and XPS insulation thickness equal to 5.08 cm (2 in.). Two #16 Gr. 420 (#5 Gr. 60) bars were
193 placed at the middle of the thickness of each wythe, and concrete compressive strength was taken
194 as 41.4 MPa (6000 psi). Shear spring elements were placed at 40.6 cm (16 in.) on center along the
195 length of the panel, starting at 20.3 cm (8 in.) in from the edge. For simplification, shear tie
196 constitutive properties for this initial investigation were modeled using *Elastic Uniaxial Material*
197 [23] rather than the prescribed multilinear approach in order to directly illustrate the effect of tie
198 stiffness on the panel response. The effect of tie ductility is illustrated later in the paper as part of
199 a realistic parametric study which will require the implementation of the multilinear shear tie
200 material model. Three levels of hypothetical tie stiffness were used to examine the effects of
201 increasing composite action: low (17.5 kN/cm), medium (43.8 kN/cm) and high (175 kN/cm). The
202 influence of panel cross-section geometry and material properties are examined in a realistic
203 prototype wall panel later in this paper.

204 The effect of increasing tie shear stiffness on the pressure-deflection and end slip response
205 is illustrated in Figure 3a and 3b, respectively. The successively darker shading between curves
206 shows the panel response trending toward the composite behavior as tie stiffness increases.
207 Similarly, end slip trends toward zero (i.e., composite response) as tie stiffness is increased. The
208 plots show that a 10-times increase in tie stiffness (low to high) increases the yield strength by
209 over 50% and decreases the panel deformation at yield by over 50%. The results therefore indicate
210 that constitutive properties of the ties have a direct influence on the overall strength and stiffness
211 of precast insulated wall panels.

212
213 Figure 3 - Computational results for a) applied pressure and b) panel end slip

214 4. PROPOSED MODEL

215 Though effective for demonstrating partially composite action, the computational model in
216 Figure 2 is more suited to research applications rather than design due to its component-based
217 assembly and computational effort. A new model for designing and analyzing partially-composite
218 precast insulated wall panels subject to lateral loading was therefore pursued. The proposed model
219 accounts for the contribution of each shear tie based on its constitutive properties and placement
220 within the panel. The model can be used for any combination of panel cross-section geometry and
221 arrangement of shear ties, including uneven and asymmetrical distributions, and is also compatible
222 with non-uniform loading conditions. It is the responsibility of the user to procure shear tie
223 constitutive relationships prior to performing the analysis. The model is currently limited to

224 statically determinate panels and further research by the authors will seek to determine efficient
225 ways to allow for the model to be compatible with indeterminate structures (e.g., multi-span wall
226 panels). A flowchart outlining the proposed model framework is shown in Figure 4. A description
227 of the procedure is followed by a validation against experimental data and comparison with the
228 previously discussed computational model.

229
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Figure 4 - Framework for proposed model

231 Before starting the procedure, two moment-curvature analyses are performed for the panel
232 cross-section as an initializing step: one assuming a composite response and the other non-
233 composite response as shown in Figure 5. The moment-curvature relationship for the composite
234 section, $M_C(\phi)$, is calculated assuming a continuous linear strain profile through the entire cross
235 section, including both concrete wythes and the sandwiched insulation layer. For these analyses,
236 the Hognestad stress-strain model [25] was used for concrete in compression; a multitude of other
237 concrete models can potentially be used as an alternative. To capture cracking, an elastic-brittle
238 concrete tensile stress-strain relationship was used, with failure at the modulus of rupture. A
239 multilinear material model was implemented for non-prestressed and prestressed steel based on a
240 fit with material test data. For the non-composite section, moment-curvature relationships are
241 calculated for both the interior, $M_{bot}(\phi)$, and exterior wythe, $M_{top}(\phi)$ and summed to obtain the non-
242 composite moment-curvature relationship, $M_{NC}(\phi)$, as shown in Equation 1. These non-composite
243 and composite responses are used as lower and upper bounds of panel strength, respectively, for
244 assessing partially-composite behavior.

$$M_{NC}(\phi) = M_{top}(\phi) + M_{bot}(\phi) \quad \text{Equation 1}$$

245 The deflections of the composite and non-composite panel configurations are determined
246 as a function of the applied load. The determination of the moment-deflection resistance of each
247 panel at non-composite and composite behavior is detailed in Figure 5 and summarized as steps A
248 through E in Figure 4. First, an incremental load, w_i is applied until the maximum moment is
249 reached at step N (step A). The resulting moment distribution is then calculated using static
250 equilibrium (step B). The curvature over the length of the panel is determined in step C for both
251 the composite and non-composite panels by combining the moment distribution from step B with
252 the moment-curvatures obtained in the aforementioned initializing step. For each incremental load,

253 the panel deflection can be computed in step D from the determined curvature distribution through
254 virtual work using Equation 2 or via other methods where $\phi_i(x)$ is the curvature over the length, L ,
255 at each load increment, w_i , and $m_\delta(x)$ is the virtual moment distribution over the length due to the
256 virtual unit force at midspan. For this model, both $\phi_i(x)$ and $m_\delta(x)$ are discretized with integration
257 points every 2.54 cm (1 in.) along the length of the panel. The user can adjust the density of
258 integration points as needed to efficiently calculate the deflection of a specific panel. Iteratively
259 incrementing the loads via steps A through D allows for the calculation of the full load-deflection
260 response of the panel with both composite and non-composite sections (step E).

261
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Figure 5 - Response estimation for composite and non-composite panels

$$\Delta_i = \int_0^L \phi_i(x) m_\delta(x) dx \quad \text{Equation 2}$$

263 To compute the load-deflection response of a partially-composite panel, $M_{PC}(\Delta)$, the
 264 iterative procedure outlined in Figure 4 and illustrated in Figure 6 is used following the completion
 265 of step E in Figure 5. This part of the procedure increments panel displacement, calculates the
 266 resulting deformation and force developed in each shear tie for the increment, and uses the shear
 267 force couple along with the non-composite moment to determine the partially-composite moment

268 at that displacement increment. An initial level of panel composite action is assumed (step F) and
269 checked for convergence upon completion of the remaining steps in the analysis (through step M).
270 For the first iteration, the non-composite panel response is used. If a specified tolerance is met, the
271 framework advances to the next displacement increment. If not, the level of composition action
272 calculated from step M is used as the initial condition for the next iteration at the same
273 displacement increment, and the calculations are repeated from step F. The program structure for
274 this analysis is presented in Figure 4 and illustrated in Figure 6.

275 For each displacement increment, i , the panel rotation at each tie location, j , is determined
276 from the respective curvature distribution (step G) using virtual work (Equation 3) or an alternative
277 method (step H). This is repeated for each iteration of composite action, k . At each tie location,
278 the shear deformation in the tie is computed from the rotation at the base of the tie (step H) and
279 compatibility as illustrated in step I (Figure 6) using Equation 4 and Equation 5. The resulting
280 shear force at each tie is determined from the tie's deformation and its mechanical properties (step
281 J). It is important to note that the shear tie load-deformation backbone curves shown in step J of
282 Figure 6 were developed as simplified approximations of test data to facilitate ease of convergence
283 and stability for the model, as previously done by Naito et al [24]. This requires the user to procure
284 test data for the given shear ties in a panel and develop the backbone curves to approximate the
285 shear tie constitutive behavior. For discrete ties, mechanical properties can be obtained either from
286 manufacturer data or experimental testing. For panels constructed with distributed ties, the force
287 contribution per length can be lumped at discrete locations and the analysis can use this same
288 procedure. Steps H through J are iterated until the contribution of all ties within the loaded half
289 span have been accounted for.

290 For ties that lie outside the span, a linear slip profile is assumed outward from the last two
291 ties within the span, and all remaining tie deformations are extrapolated accordingly. The total
292 shear force contribution of all ties on the half panel is then summed using Equation 6 (step K) and
293 multiplied by eccentricity, e , taken as the distance between wythe centroids as illustrated in Figure
294 6K, to determine the supplemental force couple caused by the shear ties. For panels with
295 asymmetrical shear tie distributions and/or non-uniform loading, the tie shear force contributions
296 are first summed from the location of the peak panel bending moment outward to either support
297 and the side with the lowest total shear force is used as a conservative estimate to calculate the
298 total supplemental moment resistance. The supplemental moment resistance is added to the non-
299 composite moment (step L) at each displacement increment with the caveat that the total partial
300 composite resistance cannot exceed the composite resistance, as shown in Equation 7. Finally, the
301 percent composite action (PCA) of the panel is determined (step M) with Equation 8. The
302 calculated PCA value is used to interpolate between the non-composite and composite moment
303 and curvature responses (see Equation 9 and 10) before the onset of the second iteration. The
304 partially-composite response curve obtained from this interpolation is then used to compute the
305 updated relative tie deformations. The procedure, Steps F to M, are iterated until the PCA at each
306 displacement step converges. This iterative procedure represents an efficient way to calculate the
307 partially-composite response of insulated wall panels.

Partially Composite Response

(F) Guess % Composite at each load step. Assume non-composite initially. Use % composite from previous step for following steps.

(G) Determine curvature along span, $\phi_{i,k}(x)$, for load step i and guess of level of composite action, step k . Interpolate partially composite moment-curvature from non-composite and composite section analysis.

(H) Utilize virtual work or other method to determine panel rotation $\theta_{i,j,k}$ at each tie location along span for given distributed load.

(I) At each tie location, j , determine the relative tie deflection, $\delta_{i,j,k}$ taking the eccentricity, e , as the distance between the centroid of each wythe.

Tie Shear Force-Deformation

(J) Determine shear force in each tie, $f_{i,j,k}$ using deflections from step (I) and constitutive tie properties.

(K) Determine total additional shear contribution from ties, $F_{i,k}$ from summation of shear forces in each tie of panel for current increment of loading, i .

(L) Superimpose moment contribution from total tie force couple ($F_{i,k} \times e$) onto non-composite moment.

(M) Calculate % composite for each load step, i , and calculate the difference from previous step, $k-1$ (or initial if $k=1$). Compare difference with tolerance. If not within tolerance, repeat iteration k .

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Figure 6 - Response estimation for partially composite panels

$$\theta_{i,j,k} = \int_0^L \phi_{i,k}(x) m_{\theta_j}(x) dx \quad \text{Equation 3}$$

310 where $\phi_{i,k}$ is the curvature distribution of the non-composite section at load increment w_i , $m_{\theta_j}(x)$ is

311 the virtual moment distribution over the length due to the applied moment at each tie location, j .

$$e = \frac{t_1}{2} + t_2 + \frac{t_3}{2} \quad \text{Equation 4}$$

$$\delta_{i,j,k} = e \tan \theta_{i,j,k} \quad \text{Equation 5}$$

312 where e is the eccentricity between the geometric centroids of each wythe and $\theta_{i,j,k}$ is the rotation
 313 at each tie location calculated using Equation 3.

$$F_{i,k} = \sum_{j=1}^N f_{i,j,k} \quad \text{Equation 6}$$

314 where N is the number of ties on the panel span and $f_{i,j,k}$ is the force in each shear tie, j , due to the
 315 deformation of each tie $\delta_{i,j,k}$ from the incrementally applied load w_i .

$$M_{PC\ i,k} = \min(M_{C\ i}, M_{NC\ i} + F_{i,k} e) \quad \text{Equation 7}$$

316 where $M_{C,i}$ is the moment capacity of the composite panel at deflection Δ_i , and $M_{NC,i}$ is the moment
 317 capacity of the non-composite panel at deflection Δ_i .

$$PCA_{i,k} = 100 \frac{M_{PC\ i,k} - M_{NC\ i}}{M_{C\ i} - M_{NC\ i}} \quad \text{Equation 8}$$

$$\phi_{PC\ i,k+1} = PCA_{i,k} (\phi_C - \phi_{NC}) + \phi_{NC} \quad \text{Equation 9}$$

$$M_{PC\ i,k+1} = PCA_{i,k} (M_C - M_{NC}) + M_{NC} \quad \text{Equation 10}$$

318 where ϕ_C , ϕ_{NC} , M_C and M_{NC} are the composite and non-composite curvature and moment response
 319 vectors, respectively.

320 5. COMPARISON WITH EXPERIMENTAL TEST DATA

321 The results of several recent experimental tests on precast insulated wall panels are used to
 322 validate the proposed model. Six wall panel configurations are considered as shown in Figure 7.
 323 Test data are obtained from Naito et al. [26], Trasborg [27] and Tomlinson and Fam [28]. Panels
 324 IWP 1 to 2 and IWP 4 to 6 measured 3.66 m (12 ft.) in total length and were subject to a uniformly
 325 distributed load within a simply-supported span of 3.05 m (10 ft.) as illustrated in Figure 7. Panel
 326 IWP 3 measured 2.7 m (8.86 ft.) in total length and was loaded in four-point bending as detailed
 327 in Figure 7. The shear ties used in each panel are shown in Table 1 and Figure 8. Shear tie

328 constitutive properties were adopted from experimental tests [24,29] and tie manufacturer
329 specifications. The tie shear force-deformation relationships are shown in Figure 9. Note that since
330 tie type D is a distributed shear tie, a tributary width of 203.2 mm (8 in.) was used to transform it
331 to into an equivalent discrete tie for use in the model. It should be noted that for the following
332 comparisons, iterations of percent composite action were stopped once the solution converged to
333 within a 1% difference of the composite action guess at each load increment.

Figure 7 - Tested insulated wall panel configurations from [26–28]

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Table 1 – Shear tie matrix

Identification	Source	Type	Material	Size
A	Thermomass®	Non-Composite (MC)	GFRP pin	MC 20/50
B	Thermomass®	Composite (CC)	GFRP pin	CC 150-50-50-50
C	Thermomass®	X Series	GFRP pin	X60-305
D	Altus Group®	C-Grid®	CFRP grid	C50 – 1.8 x 1.6
E	Tomlinson and Fam [29]	N/A	BFRP pin	B45T6

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Figure 8 - Illustration of shear ties with dimensions

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Figure 9 – Force-deformation relationships of shear ties used to construct panels

341 An illustration of the model is first used to show displacement-dependent shear tie and
342 panel behavior. Figure 10 illustrates the series of calculations that constitute the partially
343 composite member analysis. These include (a) the base rotation in each tie and the associated shear
344 deformation, (b) the force in each row of shear ties and the percentage of composite action, and
345 (c) panel pressure capacity as a function of the midspan displacement for panel IWP 4 (see Figure
346 7d). As expected, tie rotation and deformation increase with increasing panel deflections. Also,
347 Figure 10a shows that the shear ties closest to midspan (row $j=5$ – see Figure 7d) exhibit lower
348 deformation compared to those closest to the supports (row $j=1$), again as expected. The effect of
349 shear tie deformation on the force in each row is illustrated in Figure 10b. A low ductility, high
350 strength tie (type C) near the edge (row $j=1$) begins to fail at a much smaller panel deflection than
351 the remaining higher ductility ties. Strength degradation of ties in row $j=1$ has a significant
352 influence on the level of composite action (Figure 10b) as the peak row force and peak composite
353 action occur at the same panel deflection. Figure 10c further shows that the panel's lateral pressure
354 capacity is deformation-dependent. These observations are contrary to many design assumptions
355 which only consider strength limit states of insulated wall panels [30].

356 To illustrate convergence of the proposed iterative approach, the error percentage between
357 assumed and calculated percent composite values, PCA (see Equation 8), of panel IWP 4 (see
358 Figure 7) was plotted as a function of iteration step, k , for the first 25.4 mm (1 in.) of midspan
359 panel displacement in increments of 2.54 mm (0.1 in.) as shown in Figure 11. The results show
360 that for this particular example, the percent composite level for each displacement increment
361 converges to within the specified tolerance of $\pm 1\%$ composite action in ten steps or less,
362 depending on the displacement increment. It is important to note that the number of iteration steps

363 required for convergence will vary based on the complexity of the model and the tolerance
364 specified by the user.

365
366

Figure 10 - Displacement-dependent shear tie and panel behavior for IWP 4

367
 368 Figure 11 – Error percentage between assumed and calculated percent composite values as a
 369 function of iteration step, k, for the first 25.4 mm (1 in.) of panel midspan displacement for IWP

370 4

371 Figure 12 presents a comparison between the proposed model and experimental testing
 372 data for the six panels. Multiple tests were conducted on most panels, resulting in a distribution of
 373 measured response. For those panels a shaded region that bounds the experimental response is
 374 plotted. The exception is Panel IWP 3 (Figure 12c), for which only one set of data was available.
 375 Panel response calculated using the previously discussed computational modeling approach is also
 376 included in subplots a-b and d-f for additional comparison. Panel IWP 3 is not examined using
 377 computational modeling due to the use of concrete rails which encroach on the insulation layer
 378 and complicate the cross-sectional geometry. Both applied pressure and panel end slip are shown
 379 as a function of midspan deformation. The results indicate that the proposed model and
 380 computational approach show good conservative agreement with the experimental results. The

381 pressure capacity of both models trends toward the lower bound of the experimental results, and
382 end slip response from the models is larger in every case considered here. The results also compare
383 especially well for panels constructed with discrete shear ties (Figure 12a-e). The accuracy of the
384 proposed model with both experimental results and computational modeling validates the proposed
385 iteration-based model for use in predicting the response of insulated wall panels.

386
387 Figure 12 - Comparison of proposed model and the computational model with experimental data

388 for panels IWP 1 to 6 (subplots a to f, respectively)

389 **6. PARAMETRIC STUDIES**

390 The proposed model can be used to predict the response of wall panels constructed with a
391 broad range of concrete wythe cross-section geometries, insulation layer thicknesses and shear tie
392 arrangements. To illustrate the practicality of using this method as a design and analysis tool and
393 to determine the effect of tie ductility on overall panel response, two parametric studies involving
394 four hypothetical insulated wall panel configurations (Figure 13a through d) are conducted.

395 **6.1. Parametric Study A – Applicability of the model as a design tool**

396 The first study examines the applicability of the model as a design tool, incorporating the
397 effects of varying shear tie arrangements and constitutive properties on global panel response. All
398 panel configurations have the same wythe cross section geometry, overall length and simply-
399 supported span as IWP 4 (see Figure 7). The constitutive properties of the ties are depicted in
400 Figure 14. Four hypothetical tie types are considered: C, F, G, and H. Type C is a larger tie with
401 higher strength and ductility compared to the other 3, and it is used only in IWP 7 (as shown with
402 the larger tie markings in Figure 13a). Ties G and H have the same initial and unloading stiffness
403 as F but have two and three times the ductility of F, respectively. The arrangement of ties with
404 their corresponding constitutive properties are designed such that the panel IWP 7 (with tie type
405 C), IWP 8 (with tie type G), and IWP 9 (with tie type H) have comparative moment capacity. The
406 panels are examined using the proposed model. The pressure versus deformation response for all
407 panel cases is shown in Figure 15 along with the corresponding percentage of composite action at
408 the peak capacity. The results indicate that similar flexural strengths can be achieved with several
409 tie configurations, such as a few closely spaced strong connectors (IWP 7) or a larger number of
410 low strength connectors (IWP 8 and 9). Due to the high stiffness and strength of the type C ties,
411 the IWP7 panel reaches its peak strength at a much lower deformation than IWP 8 or 9, which both

412 use a denser distribution of connectors with lower strength and stiffness. The ties in Panels IWP 8
413 and 9 have the same yield strength, but the ties in IWP 9 have increased ductility and are placed
414 closer together near the end of the panel. Figure 15 shows IWP 8 and 9 with nearly the same peak
415 pressure capacity, but IWP 9 reaches a higher global panel deformation due to the increased
416 ductility. This also illustrates the effect of tie configuration, where panels with varying layouts and
417 different ties can achieve similar peak panel strength yet with significantly different panel
418 deformations. As illustrated in this parametric study, the tie properties and arrangement can be
419 used to customize the global flexibility, strength and ductility of an insulated panel in accordance
420 with a variety of design objectives.

421
422 Figure 13 – Panel configurations IWP 7-10 (a-d) used in the parametric study (all dimensions in
423 mm)

424
425 Figure 14 – Shear force-deformation relationships of shear ties used in the two parametric studies

426
427 Figure 15 – Estimated pressure-deformation response of IWP 7 through IWP 9

428 **6.2. Parametric Study B – Effect of tie ductility on global panel response**

429 In the second parametric study, a progressive shear tie failure mechanism is used to
430 illustrate the effects of tie ductility on the global composite percentage and overall response of a
431 panel. Under uniform load with simple boundary conditions, the largest inter-layer slip in an
432 idealized panel will occur at each end of the panel and approach zero at midspan. Consequently,
433 ties placed at the end of the panel will contribute more shear resistance and reach their fracture
434 deformation before ties located closer to midspan. Similarly, at later stages of the response when
435 displacements are larger, ties located closer to midspan will engage and provide increasing shear
436 contributions. To illustrate this concept, panel configuration IWP 10 (Figure 13) is analyzed with
437 three different shear ties F, G, and H (Figure 14). Figure 16a, c, and e present estimated pressure
438 – deflection responses of the IWP 10 with ties F, G and H, respectively. Three critical milestones,
439 first yield of the reinforcement, peak capacity and ultimate response (defined here as a global panel
440 deformation of 15.5 cm (6.1 in.)), are chosen to illustrate the progression of shear tie failures.
441 Figure 16b, d, and f illustrate the shear force in each tie along the length of the panel half-span
442 (due to symmetry) at the three milestones for tie type F, G, and H, respectively. When the steel
443 reinforcement in the tension wythe yields, all tie types (F-H) provide the same resistance with the
444 four connectors nearest the end of the panel in the plastic range and the others in the elastic range.
445 At this level of response, the IWP 10 tie arrangement and mechanical properties produces a panel
446 with 60% of the composite strength (i.e. milestone 1 in Figure 16a, c, and e). At the peak strength
447 of each panel (i.e. milestone 2), the majority of ties are at or near their plastic capacity. As the
448 ductility of the connectors increases, the ties can maintain the internal shear couple at larger
449 deformations and thereby allow the panels to utilize their overall flexural strength longer. For
450 example, ties G and H both enable 63% composite action at the peak capacity, versus 59% for tie

451 F. The actual strength and deformation level at peak for tie H, however, is higher than that for G
452 because both the composite and non-composite panel strengths increase at larger deformations.
453 Tie type H is able to remain stable under larger deformations than G because of the greater ductility
454 in the tie. Tie type F achieves lower composite action at peak strength because the plastic
455 deformation capacity of the tie is not large enough to allow all ties to become plastic before the
456 end tie loses strength and the panel "unzips." As the deformation increases past the peak strength,
457 progressive shear tie failures occur as illustrated in the decrease in tie strength and drop in flexural
458 capacity. For tie F, five rows of ties fail when the panel reaches the deformation of 15.5 cm (6.1
459 in.). If the ductility of the tie is doubled (tie G), three rows of ties fail - if the ductility is tripled (tie
460 H), tie integrity is maintained. Therefore, the flexural strength and percentage of composite action
461 increases at the ultimate deformation level with increases in tie ductility.

Figure 16 – Effect of progressive tie failure on performance of panel IWP 10

462
463

464 7. CONCLUSIONS

465 A simplified model was developed to assess the flexural behavior of partially-composite
466 precast concrete insulated wall panels. The approach accounts for concrete wythe flexural behavior

467 as well as the constitutive properties and geometric arrangement of the ties used to transfer shear
468 forces between the wythes. To determine the percentage of composite action between the wythes,
469 the proposed model uses an iterative method to calculate relative tie deformations and resulting
470 shear forces. These forces create force couples which are superimposed onto the non-composite
471 panel response at each iteration step as an additional moment. An OpenSees computational model
472 was also used to illustrate the accuracy of the proposed model for estimating both interface slip
473 and global flexural response. Using these two modeling approaches, the individual performance
474 of each shear tie can also be closely monitored and compared. The proposed model accurately
475 estimates the pressure-deformation and end slip response of six experimental tests representative
476 of insulated wall panel construction. Also, the proposed model and the OpenSees computation
477 model show good agreement, indicating that the approximations used in the iteration-based model
478 are acceptable.

479 Two parametric studies were performed to illustrate the effectiveness of the proposed
480 model as a simplified design and analysis tool and to show the effects on tie ductility on overall
481 panel response. Specifically, the approach was used to illustrate how tie properties and placement
482 can directly impact the global pressure-displacement response. The results of the study show that
483 constitutive properties and spatial arrangement of the tie connectors can be configured to vary the
484 panel's flexural ductility and stiffness while achieving the same strength in response to lateral
485 pressure. Tie ductility is also shown to directly impact the deformation capacity of the panel. Low
486 ductility ties result in early strength degradation of the tie, considerably reducing the level of
487 composite action as well as the panel overall deformation capacity and strength.

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